

The Post-weld Treatment of Welded Details in Bridges Using High-Frequency Mechanical Impact Theory and Practice

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ABSTRACT

The use of High-Frequency Mechanical Impact (HFMI) treatment for enhancing the fatigue strength of welded details has grown substantially during the last decade. This method will be covered in the forthcoming update of the Eurocode demonstrating its increasing recognition and acceptance within the industry.

This paper provides a brief exploration into the impact of HFMI on enhancing the fatigue life of welded details, drawing on the extensive experience gained by HiFIT[®], a leading global HFMI company in the realm of HFMI, from numerous projects where this technology has been utilized. Useful recommendations to engineers interested in HFMI treatment and several practical cases where HFMI was applied to extend the fatigue life of existing and new bridges are presented. Additionally, ongoing research initiatives investigating the latest facets of HFMI are highlighted, showcasing its potential for further development.

Keywords: High-Frequency Mechanical Impact, HFMI, Fatigue, Weld, Fracture, HiFIT.

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel bridges significantly contribute to Europe's transport infrastructure. Sweden has built over 1000 metallic and 450 composite concrete-steel bridges in the past two decades (1). Bridges are engineered for longevity, typically aiming for a service life of 80 to 120 years. Fatigue stands as a critical consideration in the design of steel bridges. In this context, the endurance of welded joints against fatigue emerges as a vital factor in the design and load rating of bridges with steel superstructure. Weldments lower the fatigue strength of steel primarily in two ways:

a. Notch effect: Weld defects, such as undercuts, act as stress raisers and initial micro-cracks and are critical to the fatigue strength in welded joints. The notch effect results in the fatigue life of a welded detail being primarily dependent on crack growth that is relatively independent of the steel's strength. For this reason, the steel class is neglected in the fatigue design of welded steel structures, and high-strength steel is seldom used in fatigue-loaded welded steel structures.

b. Welding residual stresses: Depending on several variables such as welding method, welding sequence, and the design of the detail, welding residual stresses can reach the material's yield strength. The size and distribution of welding residual stresses in a joint are generally very difficult to determine. It is usually assumed that there are tensile residual stresses at the level of the material's

yield strength as a result of welding. This means that the mean stress of a stress cycle from external load has no significance for the fatigue life of welded details.

Fatigue often dictates the maximum stress levels structural elements can safely withstand (2). Traditionally, this challenge is met by increasing the thickness of steel plates, a solution that, while effective, results in increased self-weight and higher material usage. This not only increases the construction costs but also impacts the overall sustainability of the structure. Alternatively, enhancing the fatigue strength of welded joints using post-weld treatment methods presents another solution that not only reduces material usage but also lowers the self-weight of the structure and thus stresses from permanent loads.

2 POST-WELD TREATMENT METHODS

If the fatigue strength of a welded joint is not governed by root cracking, an improvement in the fatigue resistance can be achieved through post-weld treatment, often based on one (or a combination) of these measures: (a) reducing the geometric stress concentration at the transition between the base metal and weld material, (b) removing local notches (e.g. undercuts) along the weld toe, (c) relaxing the tensile residual stresses and, if possible, introduce compressive residual stresses in the area around the weld toe.

Post-weld treatment methods are divided into two main categories. The first category includes methods that primarily reduce the stress concentration at the weld toe. This is achieved by removing local notches and a geometry change (a combination of “a” and “b” above). Several post-weld treatment techniques have been endorsed by the International Institute of Welding (IIW) to enhance the fatigue strength of welded joints in this category. Notably, mechanical treatments such as burr grinding or thermal treatments like Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) remelting are prominent among these methods. Burr grinding is a well-known and relatively old method where the weld toe is ground with a rotating file or grinding pin to remove local notches and irregularities, and thus achieve a smoother transition between the weld and base material. In TIG dressing, a tungsten electrode is used to reheat and remelt the material in the weld toe area. As a result, a smoother transition between weld and base material is obtained with reduced stress concentration. In addition, the remelting causes the weld undercuts and other local weld defects to merge, leading to improved fatigue strength. TIG dressing also refines the material’s microstructure and enhances its mechanical properties. According to earlier versions of the IIW's guidelines (3), these methods could lead to a 50% increase in fatigue strength. This increase equated to an impressive threefold enhancement in the fatigue life of the treated component. Nevertheless, the recent updates (4) in the IIW guidelines suggest a more conservative fatigue strength improvement of 30%. Despite this revision, both methods—burr grinding and TIG remelting—play a crucial role in enhancing the fatigue resistance of welds. For both burr grinding and TIG dressing, IIW suggests instructions to thoroughly inspect the details to verify the quality. While burr grinding and TIG remelting are effective, their practicality for bridge applications is limited due to the need for highly skilled operators and the time-consuming nature of these processes, with an average speed of less than 150 mm/min. These constraints along with the stringent inspections after the treatment often render these methods less viable for large-scale structures like bridges.

The second category of post-weld treatment includes methods that result in the relaxation of detrimental tensile residual stresses at the weld toe, for example, through heat treatment (annealing), and mechanical methods that induce local compressive stresses at the weld toe, the latter being more practical in bridge structures. The most effective method in this category is High-Frequency Mechanical Impact treatment which has gained a great deal of attention in recent years.

3 HIGH-FREQUENCY MECHANICAL IMPACT (HFMI) TREATMENT

HFMI describes a treatment process where the steel (weld toe) is hammered with a high-strength steel indenter at a high frequency. The technique is a further development of the old 'hammer peening' and

'needle peening' and stands out as a pivotal advancement in improving the fatigue life of metallic weldments. HFMI primarily works through three mechanisms:

a. Inducing compressive residual stress at the weld toe: which effectively prevents/delays crack initiation and slows down the rate of crack propagation. Even though compressive residual stresses at the weld toe rapidly diminish from the treated surface, they are highly beneficial and account for the main part of the method's higher efficiency compared to burr grinding and TIG treatment (see Figure 1). The fact that local compressive stresses have such an effect in HFMI-treated welds results from the fatigue life being altered from being primarily a function of crack growth to including a significant crack initiation phase. An important consequence of this is that the dependency of fatigue strength on the steel's strength is restored. In other words, HFMI treatment has a greater effect when applied to welded constructions with high-strength steel.

b. Enhancing the local weld geometry by increasing the weld toe radius: this alteration, as illustrated in Figure 1, in the weld geometry is instrumental in mitigating stress concentration, thereby contributing significantly to the overall improvement in fatigue strength.

c. Material hardening in the treatment area: the cold work due to HFMI boosts the steel's hardness in the treatment region, thereby increasing resistance against fatigue crack initiation and propagation. The plastic deformations due to cold work also eliminate the weld defects such as undercuts in the weld toe. A positive outcome of removing the initial imperfections is to account for the significant contribution of the crack initiation phase in fatigue resistance. This results in a flatter slope of S-N curves for HFMI-treated joints, which is especially important for constructions operating in high-cycle fatigue with relatively low stress ranges such as bridges.

The high frequency of impacts in HFMI results in considerably smaller distances between impact points providing a more uniform treatment and more consistent induction of compressive residual stresses at relatively greater depths compared to regular hammer peening. Moreover, HFMI causes less noise and vibrations, making it more user-friendly. Numerous studies have proven the efficacy of HFMI in enhancing fatigue resistance in both new and existing bridges, marking its versatility and broad applicability.

Figure 1. Three beneficial effects generated by HFMI treatment of welds

4 HiFIT

HiFIT[®] is a world-leading company and a globally renowned brand in supplying HFMI treatment equipment and services. HiFIT provides equipment for manual and robotic HFMI treatments as well as various pins for different purposes, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Unlike most HFMI devices available on the market that are based on ultrasonic technology, HiFIT's devices are pneumatically driven allowing for smaller, lighter, and more compact designs. HFIT devices operate at high frequencies in the range of 180-300 Hz. The latest HFMI device in HiFIT's production line, HF21R-S (Figure 2a) is the most compact HFMI tool on the market. This device incorporates an advanced damping system to ensure remarkably low accelerations of just below 3.9 m/s² on the handle, surpassing its competitors.

Figure 2. HiFIT device for (a) manual and (b) automated robotic treatment and (c) different treatment pins with various tip diameters

The device's advanced cooling system guarantees consistently low operating temperatures in different working conditions, offering a long-lasting tool with minimal wear. Its lightweight and ergonomic design contributes to making it the fastest-operating HFMI tool, achieving a record treatment speed of 1.36 m/min.

5 IMPACT OF HFMI TREATMENT ON THE DESIGN AND THE USE OF HIGH-STRENGTH STEEL

In the recommendations for HFMI treatment issued by IIW (5), there are guidelines for the impact of the base material's yield strength on the fatigue strength for HFMI-treated welds. These allow a 12.5 percent increase in fatigue strength (one FAT class) for every 200 MPa increase in yield strength of the base material. For steel S355 or lower, fatigue strength can be increased by four FAT classes. A maximum increase of eight FAT classes can be credited for steels with yield strength higher than 950 MPa with a maximum allowable C-class of C180. Figure 3a shows the number of increases in C-classes as a function of yield strength (f_y).

Figure 3b presents examples of S-N curves (nominal stress) for HFMI-improved welds in low-strength steel ($f_y < 355$ MPa). The value in "()" represents the fatigue class (C-class) for welds in as-welded condition according to Hobbacher (6). Consider the case with a welded joint in low-strength steel ($f_y < 355$ MPa) which in as-welded condition would be classified as C90 ($m = 3$). HFMI treatment raises the fatigue strength to C140 with a slope $m = 5$. If this weld is subjected to a stress range of 100 MPa, a lifespan of approximately 1.5 million cycles is achieved for an untreated weld, and a lifespan of more than 10 million cycles for an HFMI treated, that is, a lifespan increase of more than seven times compared to the untreated weld.

If the same example as above is taken, where a joint with C-class C90 ($m=3$) is now upgraded to high-strength steel ($550 \text{ MPa} \leq f_y < 750 \text{ MPa}$) and thereafter HFMI treated, then according to the recommendation, the fatigue strength will be increased by 6 FAT classes equivalent to C180 ($m=5$), which corresponds to a lifespan increase of more than 200 times compared to an untreated weld if considering high-cycle fatigue. Alternatively, the fatigue load can be increased by 100 percent (C90

to C180) to achieve the same lifespan as an untreated weld. This can be interpreted as considerable material saving because the allowable stresses in the joint are suddenly doubled.

Figure 3. (a) Fatigue strength improvement as a function of steel yield strength and (b) Characteristic fatigue curves (in nominal stress) for FAT90 in as-welded condition and FAT140 after HFMI treatment in low-strength steel ($f_y < 355$ MPa). The value in parentheses "(") represents the detail category (fatigue curve) for welds in untreated condition (5)

In a fatigue-loaded structure, such as a bridge, there is usually a small number of details with relatively low fatigue strengths that are decisive in fatigue design. The possibility of increasing the fatigue strength of these details can have a significant effect on the amount of utilized steel in a bridge. This was demonstrated by Shams-Hakimi (7) in a welded steel railway bridge where the author showed that through the utilization of HFMI, a considerable material saving of 30% can be achieved.

6 IMPORTANT CONSIDERATIONS IN POST-WELD TREATMENT WITH HFMI

Although HFMI treatment brings several positive effects to a welded joint, such as the removal of microcracks, smoother transition with lower stress concentration, and material hardening, the induced compressive residual stresses at the weld toe account for a significant part of the method's superior effect compared to other post-weld treatment methods. To be able to credit the aforementioned increase in fatigue strength suggested, it is important to verify that there is no risk of relaxation of these residual stresses during the construction's lifespan. A relaxation of the compressive residual stresses from the HFMI treatment can occur as a result of overloads. In principle, a single overload with a sufficiently high-stress peak is enough to relax these residual stresses partially or completely due to local plasticization. Another effect that should be considered in the fatigue design of HFMI-treated joints is the impact of mean stress. For example, high mean stress due to significant self-weight combined with variable stress ranges from the fatigue load can cause relaxation of the compressive residual stresses in the joints in the same way as overloads. Road bridges are an example of structures with relatively high mean stress where there is a risk of overload from heavy vehicles. One way to neutralize the negative effect of the bridge's self-weight is to perform the HFMI treatment after the bridge is constructed.

In any case, HFMI treatment imposes new requirements on fatigue design because, in addition to the stress range, which is usually the only parameter to consider on the load effect side, the impact of mean stress and possible overloads must also be considered. The design also depends on the choice of steel strength, which is not the case for untreated steel structures. The possibility of fractures in other fatigue-critical areas than the weld toe must also be considered. If the weld root becomes more critical than the weld toe for fatigue fractures, the HFMI treatment cannot be utilized to its full

potential. Therefore, it is important to consider this aspect in the design and avoid root cracking by appropriate measures such as increasing the weld throat or the weld's depth of penetration.

7 REQUIREMENTS TO APPLY HFMI AND QUALITY CONTROL

The IIW recommendations for HFMI treatment (5) include comprehensive instructions on how the treatment should be carried out as well as how the quality of the treatment should be evaluated and assured. The weld quality before treatment should be satisfactory. Weld seam and adjacent base material should be completely free of slag without traces of oxides, weld spatter, and splashes, as well as other foreign materials. The weld before HFMI treatment should meet the acceptance requirements for weld quality B in ISO 5817. However, this does not mean that the weld must meet all criteria in quality level B but only weld profile-related quality criteria. If the weld profile does not comply with these acceptance requirements, surface grinding is recommended before HFMI treatment. However, it should be noted that grinding operations that make it difficult for the HFMI operator to distinguish the exact location of the weld toe should be avoided.

Over-treatment of the weld with HFMI should also be avoided. However, the method is robust in the sense that under- or over-treatment within the treated area still results in a significant increase in fatigue life. The resulting HFMI groove must be smooth along all welds that have been treated. A smooth and shiny groove without traces of lines characterizes a correctly treated weld toe. No lines originating from the heat-affected zone should be visible in the groove. A linear crack similar to the one shown in *Figure 4a* is an indication that the weld has not been treated with the correct procedure. HFMI-groove must be continuous and preferably without traces of individual impacts, see *Figure 4b*.

Figure 4. (a) shows a linear crack that reduces or eliminates the effect of the HFMI treatment, (b) shows a defect-free groove but with individual areas that are treated where further treatment is required to achieve a smooth groove (5).

Figure 5. Inappropriately conducted treatment with a sharp edge resembling a crack-like feature

Figure 6. The HFMI groove after the treatment of the weld toe should be at least $d=0.1-0.2$ mm deep

If the treatment cannot be performed without interruption, it is recommended to restart the operation at least 10 mm behind the interruption point. HFMI treatment leads to large local plastic deformations at the weld toe. If the pin is positioned so that it treats only a specific area, the resulting plastic deformation of the metal can cause crack-like defects adjacent to the HFMI groove, see *Figure 5*. Such types of defects should be removed by light grinding followed by additional HFMI treatment in that specific area. The depth of the HFMI groove is an excellent measure of the degree of treatment. A minimum depth of between 0.1 – 0.2 mm is necessary to guarantee proper treatment of the weld toe, see *Figure 6*.

8 PRACTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Effective communication stands as the cornerstone of projects involving High-Frequency Mechanical Impact (HFMI) treatments. The precision, clarity, and depth of communication among all parties involved—ranging from engineers to field workers—are imperative for the successful application of HFMI. Structural drawings serve a pivotal role in this communicative process, carefully outlining the areas designated for HFMI treatment, thereby ensuring a shared and comprehensive understanding of the treatment’s scope.

On another front, economic considerations and detailed project planning are crucial for maximizing efficiency and minimizing operational costs. The sequence in which HFMI treatments are integrated with welding and subsequent processing activities requires careful planning to avoid unnecessary downtime, thereby optimizing the use of labor and facilities. The proactive engagement of HFMI providers from the early stages of a project is instrumental, enabling the simulation of treatments in scenarios where accessibility might be restricted, see *Figure 7*. This foresight not only assures that desired outcomes are attainable but also mitigates the risk of delays and budget overruns. Moreover, a keen awareness of manufacturing conditions and potential design requirements, such as the strategic placement of lashing points, is essential to maintain the integrity and effectiveness of HFMI treatments without compromising the project's structural durability.

Figure 7. Simulation of access for HFMI treatment in joints with limited access

9 FIELD APPLICATIONS

9.1 Hising Bridge in Gothenburg, Sweden

The Hising Bridge, constructed in 2019, serves as a landmark in downtown Gothenburg, Sweden, enhancing connectivity between the central city and Hisingen Island. Spanning 440 meters in length and 40 meters in width, this bridge accommodates tram, vehicle, bicycle, and pedestrian traffic. It features a movable section with a central lift span of 48 meters to allow maritime passage, weighing 800 tons. The project prioritized sustainability, aligning with environmental objectives and aiming for a design that is both lightweight and durable, with a particular focus on fatigue resistance. Two critical areas were identified for potential fatigue issues and additional weight: the movable deck and the steel structure that connects the box girders to the concrete pillars, see *Figure 8*.

Figure 8. HFMI treatment of Hising bridge (a) steel components in the supports and (b) orthotropic deck in the lift span

The HFMI method was chosen by the project's designers and contractors, a joint venture between Skanska and MT Højgaard, to improve the fatigue strength of welded joints and to reduce the weight of the movable span. This span incorporated a 2-meter high orthotropic system, and the client aimed for a lightweight design. In total, over 1000 meters of welds, primarily the connections between the ribs and cross beams, were treated in the project. Despite challenges such as confined spaces and interruptions from regular bridge openings during the day, the project was completed in 12 days. Post-weld treatment was also applied to the "V" shaped steel components connecting the steel box girders to concrete pillars, improving their fatigue resistance. The welds between the inclined plates and the base plate were treated using HFMI.

9.2 Kalvholms Bridge in Karlstad, Sweden

HiFIT Scandinavia was involved in the HFMI treatment of the Kalvholms Bridge in Karlstad, Sweden in 2023 (see Figure 9). The project was conducted in collaboration with WSP as the designer.

Figure 9. HFMI treatment of the new Kavholms bridge where the welded connections between the web stiffeners and web plats were treated

Critical details including welded flange and web splices, and the connections between the web stiffeners and the flanges/webs of the girders, were treated with HiFIT to ensure the bridge's adequate service life.

9.3 Bridge 22-265-1 in Stöde, Sweden

Bridge 22-265-1, built in 1964, is a three-span continuous steel girder bridge with a concrete deck. The bridge needed strengthening to meet heavy traffic requirements (BK4 level according to the Swedish standard). The strengthening work involved welding extra plates to flanges of the existing girders and adding new stiffeners to the webs (see Figure 10).

By performing HFMI on the new welded details, the fatigue resistance of the welds was substantially increased to accommodate the new levels of stress in the bridge components.

Figure 10. HFMI treatment of the existing bridge 22-265-1 where the welded connections between the newly added web stiffeners and web plates as well as new flange stiffener plates and girder flanges were treated

9.4 A New Railway Bridge, Sweden

Bridge 3500-2437-1 is a new railway bridge over Örbyhusån river in Sweden. It is a simply supported girder bridge with a total length of 10.9m and a clear span of 9.9m. Treatments were conducted on web stiffeners, flange connectors, and lifting hooks to improve the fatigue strength of welds (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. HFMI treatment of welded details in a new railway bridge including the welded connections between the web stiffeners and web plates, connection plates of flanges as well as lifting hooks

9.5 A New Railway Bridge, Switzerland

Production of a new railway bridge in Aigle, Switzerland involved HFMI treatment (Figure 12). The Burignion Bridge, an 18m long railway bridge located in Chardonne in Switzerland, near Lake Geneva was found to be in critical condition after signs of fatigue cracks. In 2010, the old bridge was replaced by a new one. The K-seams along the bridge were treated with HFMI using HiFIT technology during the manufacturing phase to enhance the fatigue life of the new bridge.

Figure 12. HFMI treatment of welded details in a new railway bridge in Switzerland

9.6 An Existing Road Bridge, Germany

Refurbishment of the federal road bridge B100 in Anhalt, Germany, involved the HFMI treatment of an orthotropic deck system as shown in Figure 13. The welds between the ribs and deck plate as well as the cross beams were treated using HiFIT technology to enhance the fatigue life of the bridge.

Figure 13. HFMI treatment of welded details in an existing bridge in Germany

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